

TWENTY-SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS
(ICCM22)**Experimental and Numerical Determination of the Mode II Fracture Toughness of Woven Composites**Rowan Healey ^{a*}, Nabil M Chowdhury ^a, Wing Kong Chiu ^a, John Wang ^b^aDepartment of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Monash University, Clayton, Victoria 3800, Australia^bAerospace Division, Defence Science and Technology Group, 506 Lorimer Street, Fishermans Bend, Victoria 3207, Australia**ABSTRACT**

The desire to reduce the weight of aircraft structures has led to significant increases in the presence of fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites (FRPMC). As a result, failure prediction tools such as fatigue spectra have become more relevant in regards to fatigue life predictions. When considering fatigue in composite materials, fracture toughness is an important measure due to its use in crack growth and failure estimation. While adequate techniques and an ASTM standard for unidirectional FRPMC exist, there are mixed opinions when investigating woven FRPMC. This study describes a three-dimensional finite element model developed to assist in determining the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IIc}) of fibre reinforced woven composites, validated by an experimental and numerical comparison of G_{IIc} determination for unidirectional FRPMC. Two numerical methods were employed due to their prominence in literature: displacement field, and the J integral. Numerically determined unidirectional G_{IIc} values were verified with experimental results, leading to the successful employment and extension to woven composites which displayed similar agreement.

Keywords

Durability, delamination, fatigue, three-point-bending, composites

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to their high strength and relatively low weight, composite materials are continually being developed for use in structures particularly in the aerospace industry. As such this signals a need for understanding their common failure modes and how to efficiently test their properties, so that damage tolerance guidelines can be produced. A common means of failure for polymer matrix composites is delamination, which refer to crack propagation due separation of layers as a result of matrix failure[1]. As the crack propagates, energy is dissipated during the creation of fracture surfaces, a means of measuring this is the strain energy release rate (SERR) [2]. Mode II delamination (shearing) specifically has been broadly analysed with testing methods such as the end notch flexure (ENF) test and ASTM D7905-14 test being developed for unidirectional carbon-fibre composites [3]. Examination of these testing methods was performed by Kunigal N Shivakumar et al. [4] who compared the ENF, ASTM and Japanese Industrial Standard (JIS) standards. Shivakumar et al. found the JIS method to be a mixed mode I-II test which underestimated mode II fracture toughness (G_{IIc}), while values for G_{IIc} measured by ENF and ASTM methods were close to equal. With the benefit of an expression for compliance, the ASTM standard provided assistance for investigating crack growth experienced under fatigue loading [4]. Similar methodologies to the ASTM D7905 have seen implementation for woven materials, such as A.B. Pereira et al. [5] who initially conducted Finite Element Analysis (FEA) to choose stacking sequence for woven fabric glass/epoxy multidirectional laminates.

The measurement of the mode II SERR for composites has been the focus of many studies [5, 6], however the comparison of experimental and numerical methods between different composites has yet to be examined. This study aims to compare experimentally obtained values of G_{IIc} for one type of

unidirectional fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites (FRPMC) with that of numerically obtained values through displacement field and the J-Integral method using ABAQUS CAE. This technique is then used to validate a comparison between previously mentioned numerical methods and experimental results for a woven FRPMC.

2.0 EXPERIMENTAL AND MODELLING METHODS

2.1 Composite Material Setup

A number of ENF specimens 177.8mm long (7 inch) were manufactured using two different materials. Both of which contained a 76.2mm (3 inch) long crack, achieved by using a 0.0127mm thick polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE/Teflon) insert located mid-plane of the laminate to simulate a 3 inch long initial crack.

The unidirectional specimen consists of IM7/977-3 carbon fibre prepreg [7]. All specimens are 30 plies thick with uniform thickness at each step with a stacking sequence of $[0]^{30}$ in accordance with the ASTM standard D 5687/D 5687M [8].

The woven specimen comprises of a M18/1/G939 carbon fibre prepreg with a satin weave [9]. All specimens are 16 plies thick with uniform thickness at each step with a cross ply stacking sequence of $[(0/90)/(+45/-45)]_{4s}$ in accordance with the ASTM standard D5687/D5687M [8].

Table 1 Elastic constants and strengths for: IM7/997-3 carbon epoxy unidirectional lamina with a 60% fiber volume fraction, and elastic constants for IM7-977-3 [7].

	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	ν_{12}	Tensile Strength			Compressive Strength	
						σ_{11} (MPa)	σ_{22} (MPa)	σ_{12} (MPa)	σ_{11} (MPa)	σ_{22} (MPa)
IM7-977-3	161	8.3	5.3	5.3	0.24	2630	84	82	1680	281

Table 2 Material properties of HexPly M18/1/G939 carbon fibre prepreg [10]

	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	ν_{12}	Tensile Strength			Compressive Strength	
						σ_{11} (MPa)	σ_{22} (MPa)	σ_{12} (MPa)	σ_{11} (MPa)	σ_{22} (MPa)
M18/G939	65	67	4.0	4.0	0.04	800	800	100	800	800

2.2 Experimental Setup

Static testing was performed using an INSTRON 1342 machine with a 100 kN load cell enabling the recording of load and displacement values. A three-point bend test rig was held in position by the machines actuator and specimens were then placed in the rig at positions coinciding with the ASTM standard D7905/D7905M [3] testing procedure for fracture testing and compliance calibration. The experimental testing performed uses the pre-cracked specimens for CC.

Fracture testing was performed by loading the specimens at a rate of 0.5mm/min [3] until delamination propagated to the centre of the specimen and then further until catastrophic failure.

Prior to testing specimens, an optical microscope was used to detect the initial crack tip (end of the Teflon).

TWENTY-SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS
(ICCM22)

CC was performed by adjusting the specimen such that the crack length was equal to 20mm, 30mm, 37.3mm and 40mm [3] and then loading at a rate of 0.5mm/min until a position corresponding to $\leq 50\%$ of the critical displacement was reached. The specimen was then unloaded and repositioned at a different crack length and retested [3].

2.3 Three-dimensional Numerical Models

An ABAQUS model of the specimen was created to perform a numerical comparison to experimental results, with the intent of validating numerical determination of G_{IIc} . The model was composed of a specimen part consisting of a 30 ply layup (unidirectional) which was a solid extrude with composite layups. Rollers were modelled as solid half cylinders using the known dimensions of the experimental test rig with material properties of hardened steel. The friction coefficient between the rollers and the surface of the specimens used was 0.01 [11], to prevent sliding of the specimen during loading.

A crack seam was implemented to represent the crack, located 76.2mm away from the left edge (crack front). The intent was to create a gap between the seam and surface interface allowing for a PTFE interface (Normal Hard Contact) to be enforced between the two specimen mid-planes.

The region in close proximity to the crack tip was finely meshed through the use of biased seeding along with sweep control to enable the localised stress and displacement to be accurately represented [12]. Application of a pinned boundary condition to the supporting rollers was used to ensure that there was no translation, while a displacement boundary condition was applied to the centre of the specimen to prevent sliding.

Numerical simulations were conducted for the fracture testing, J-Integral and displacement field. Initially two-dimensional FEA models were constructed to perform numerical analysis with the selected techniques in order to gauge their accuracy in a timely manner.

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 Fracture Testing

Mode II fracture testing was performed as set out in the ASTM D7905 [3], the span between the support rollers of the 3 point bending test rig was 100mm with rollers of radius 10mm the test was conducted at $a_0=37.3\text{mm}$. The IM7/977-3 and M18/1/G939 specimens were both then loaded and unloaded at the same rate after catastrophic failure. Load-displacement data was recorded for the duration of testing. The resulting data is shown in Figure 3 where the average load displacement curves for several unidirectional and woven specimens continue for the entirety of testing.

Figure 1: Average load displacement curves for fracture testing of unidirectional and woven specimens until catastrophic failure

At the first peak of the curves the crack proceeds to the centre roller hence resulting in a “drop” which corresponds to a change in the materials compliance [3], ASTM D7905 loads the specimens at 50% of the peak values to model the CC testing parameters to ensure that delamination doesn’t propagate, allowing for multiple tests to be conducted on a single specimen.

3.2 Compliance Calibration

CC for the pre-cracked (PC) specimens was completed as per ASTM D7905 [3]. Specimens were loaded at a nominal rate of 0.5mm/min and unloaded at the same rate, while maximum loading conditions were determined from the fracture results. Hence several crack lengths were tested. Force displacement curves were constructed for CC as they were for fracture testing, the difference in gradient (compliance) follows with the change in crack length.

Next, the CC coefficients were calculated for each crack length, with only the linear region of load-displacement data being utilized and not potential nonlinearities present at the beginning of testing [3]. The resulting parameters of A and m were found using a linear least squares linear regression as well as the correlation coefficient: r^2 . This analysis enabled for the fitting of the force vs displacement data at each individual crack length, corresponding to discrete values of both displacement and force.

The compliance for each crack length C was then plotted with the cube of the crack length a^3 and subsequently fitted by the same statistical method [3, 13].

$$C = A + ma^3 \quad \text{(Equation 1)}$$

This produced a relation between the compliance and the crack length which can be used to determine the SERR, using:

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{3mP_c^2 a_0^2}{2B} \quad \text{(Equation 2)}$$

The ASTM D7905 assumes that the strain energy release rate distribution along the crack front is uniform, this behaviour isn’t exhibited by multidirectional laminates due to the effects of bending-

extension/bending-shearing/twisting-extension coupling [14]. Hence relations developed for carbon/epoxy woven composites by Morais and Pereira [5] which have seen much application were utilised for the woven specimens[15-17]:

$$G_{II} = \frac{9P^2 a_e^2}{16b^2 E_1 h^3} \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

Figure 2: Least square linear fit of compliance and the cube of the crack length data, for the unidirectional and woven specimens

Figure 2 shows compliance calibration curves for both types of specimen, though only the unidirectional variants were used with equation 2 to find G_{IIc} . The gradient of the unidirectional curve (m) resulted in a G_{IIc} value of $\sim 1175.85 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$ while equations suiting the woven specimen which were described by Reis et al. [18] produced a G_{IIc} value of $\sim 1408.11 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$.

3.3 ABAQUS Compliance Calibration (Unidirectional)

Mimicking the ASTM D7905 compliance testing, the ABAQUS FEA models were statically loaded with different crack lengths. Load displacement data was output and similarly to the experimental procedure the compliance was calculated and subsequently fit to Equation 1, enabling for the calculation of G_{IIc} . A G_{IIc} value of 1238.45 Jm^{-2} was obtained.

3.4 ABAQUS Displacement Field (Unidirectional)

The displacement field method uses the relative change in horizontal and vertical displacement of nodes after application of a load. By probing before and after the loading roller was displaced, the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness can be determined [11].

The resulting G_{IIc} estimates at each node were compared against the corresponding distance from the crack tip. A linear extrapolation was then performed to find the y intercept which corresponds to the G_{IIc} approximation. As the radial distance decreases the calculated value of G_{IIc} approached a singularity [19] hence values far enough from the crack tip such that no exponential behaviour was present were chosen for the linear fit. The resulting G_{IIc} value was determined to be $\sim 1116.83 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$ for the three-dimensional unidirectional model.

3.5 ABAQUS J Integral (Unidirectional):

The J-Integral is a two-dimensional contour integral which encloses the crack tip, while possessing starting and finishing points on the crack faces. It is commonly used to determine the energy release rate observed with the growth of a crack [20]. A region on either side of the crack tip had its mesh refined to ensure that there was no significant discontinuities in the mesh sizing[21], a biasing factor of 1.2 was applied along the radius of a circle of radius 0.005 m with the mesh concentrated towards the crack tip using C3D6 elements.

Figure 3: A zoomed in view of the mesh pattern close to the crack tip used when performing the J integral in ABAQUS

Due to the J integral functionality in ABAQUS, a sweeping mesh was implemented around the crack tip rather than a structured mesh as shown in Figure 3. Five contours were constructed to produce five G_{IIc} (J integral) values, each had a circular/curved shape. The average unidirectional G_{IIc} value of all contours was 1283.99 Jm^{-2} with a standard deviation of 84.5 Jm^{-2} between contours.

3.6 ABAQUS Woven:

Following the application of numerical testing to the FEA model with unidirectional material properties, said properties were then adjusted to that of the woven material to enable the determination of G_{IIc} . Numerous analytical methods were chosen to provide a means for experimentally determining G_{IIc} ; Paulo N.B. Reis et al utilised a modified crack length measure which was calculated from the specimen compliance[18], Toshio Ogasawara et al used the more common conjugate beam analysis which takes the peak load and displacement into account[22], A.B. Pereira fit the compliance calibration data to a third order equation and using the resulting parameters calculated G_{IIc} [23], and the ASTM D7905 standard which was intended for unidirectional ENF specimens. Due to the agreement between the numerical results for the unidirectional model, an extension of both displacement field and the J integral for the woven ABAQUS model was made.

**TWENTY-SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS
(ICCM22)**

Table 3 Summary of Unidirectional Specimen G_{IIc} values (Jm^{-2}) across both analytical and numerical methods.

	Analytical Method	Numerical Methods (FEA)		
	ASTM7905	ABAQUS CC	J Integral	Displacement Field
G_{IIc} (Jm^{-2})	1175.85	1238.45	1283.99	1116.83

Table 4 Summary of Woven Specimen G_{IIc} values across both analytical and numerical methods.

	Analytical Methods			Numerical Methods (FEA)		
	Paulo N.B. Reis	Toshio Ogasawara	A.B. Pereira	ASTM7905	J Integral	Displacement Field
G_{IIc} (Jm^{-2})	1408.11	1546.72	1422.9	995.07	1302.78	1465.3

With exception of the ASTM D7905, all analytical methods reside within 10% of one another providing an acceptable range for the numerical results to fall into. The ASTM D7905 demonstrated a significant underestimation of G_{IIc} with a value of $995.07 Jm^{-2}$. The J integral and displacement field elastic results both fell within the analytical range with values of $1302.78 Jm^{-2}$ and $1465.3 Jm^{-2}$ respectively.

4.0 DISCUSSION:

The linear behaviour between displacement and load characteristic of the elastic region was initially observed in the static testing (Figure 1), this was followed by a steep drop in load corresponding to crack growth to the loading roller. While this was less pronounced for the woven specimens, the subsequent decrease in the gradient of the load-displacement curve indicates that the specimen experienced damage (further confirmed by visual inspection). Both the unidirectional and woven specimens displayed good linear behaviour. G_{IIc} was found to be $1174.9 Jm^{-2}$ for the unidirectional specimen, however the ASTM D7905 was not designed for woven FRPMC specimens hence equation 3 described by Reis et al [18] (amongst others) was utilised to calculate G_{IIc} to be $1408.1 Jm^{-2}$. As both specimen values were determined by experimentally dependable means they were used as a basis by which to compare the numerical results.

Agreement was found between the two-dimensional numerical models, however it is the author's intent to implement progressive damage in a three-dimensional model. Hence to ensure the FEA model was representative, focus was placed on three-dimensions. Testing performed on the unidirectional specimens in order to validate the numerical model displayed good accuracy, with all results lying within 10% of the experimental values. The J-integral possessed high similarity through the thickness of the model (comparing the same contours), with a notable standard deviation of $84.45 Jm^{-2}$ across all contours with an average G_{IIc} of $\sim 1284 Jm^{-2}$. Hence transitioning from two-dimensions to three didn't poorly affect the J-integrals accuracy, though the excessive stiffness of the model does reiterate the importance of progressive damage models. Displacement field on the other hand produced an estimate within 5% of the experimental value ($1116.83 Jm^{-2}$) which underestimates G_{IIc} . Therefore while displacement field displayed the most favourable results when compared to the G_{IIc} experimental values,

implementation of a progressive damage model is expected to provide a less stiff J-integral estimate as well as a further decreases for displacement field.

The agreement between experimental and numerical unidirectional results justified using the ABAQUS FEA model with woven material parameters. As literature devoted to fibre reinforced polymer matrix woven composites is significantly less prominent than unidirectional composites and there is no standard for determining G_{IIc} for woven composites, several methods described by papers have been implemented for comparison. Of the three analytical methods examined [18, 22, 23], all are within 10% of each other. As with the unidirectional material, the woven FEA results were similar to the analytical values.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Through application of the ASTM D7905, a series of static tests were conducted in order to determine G_{IIc} of 1M7/977-3 to be 1175.85 Jm^{-2} . Two numerical methods implemented using ABAQUS CAE, which can predict G_{IIc} were then compared against this experimentally determined value. While the J integral produced results within 10% of the experimental results, the notably high variance between the inner and outer contours ($\sigma^2=84.45 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$) suggests sensitivity to mesh density (in three-dimensions) as the contours increase in size so does the estimate of G_{IIc} . Similarly the J integral results also indicated that implementation of a progressive damage model would likely benefit G_{IIc} numerical predictions due to the relatively high stiffness exhibited (1284 Jm^{-2}). The general agreement between experimental and current numerical results justified extending the numerical modelling to the woven specimen. The resulting woven analysis demonstrated agreement between several analytical sources and the implemented numerical methods. The intended use of this comparison and extension is to provide an alternative to experimentation for determination of G_{IIc} , enabling specimen allocation to be more heavily weighted to fatigue testing.

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**TWENTY-SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS
(ICCM22)**

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